

**AN ASSESSMENT OF THE DURABILITY PROPERTIES OF FERROCEMENT BASED
POLYMER MODIFIED SILICA FUME CONCRETE**

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ABSTRACT. In recent days, many novel types of concrete are being developed and research is on a daily basis, since modern civil engineering constructions require higher strength and durability. This study has made an attempt to research on ferrocement based polymer modified concrete with silica fume as a replacement of cement. Welded wire mesh and chicken wire mesh are used in one and two layers, with 3% polymer addition and silica fume is used as a replacement for cement by 0%, 5%, 10%, 15%, 20%, 25% and 30%. A mix design for M30 is designed referring to IS 10262-2019 Code book. At 15% replacement of cement by silica fume, 3% polymer addition and combination of welded wire mesh and chicken wire mesh in two layers gave optimum results for compression, flexure and shear after the effect of acidic attack, sulphate attack and chloride attack.

KEYWORDS. Polymer, Ferrocement, Silica fume, Compressive strength, Flexural strength, Shear strength, Acidic attack, Sulphate attack, Chloride attack.

INTRODUCTION.

The idea of using polymers in cement – based materials dates back to early 1920s when the first patents on using natural rubber polymer – modified cementitious systems were issued [11]. The first patent on the use of synthetic rubber latexes in such application was used in 1932 America, latex – modified concrete (LMC) was used as a bridge overlay in Michigan as early as 1958. In Ontario, the first major application of LMC was a 1980 overlay on collector lanes of highway 401 in North York. Polymer modified mortar and concrete are prepared by mixing either a polymer or monomer in a dispersed, powdery, or liquid form with fresh cement mortar and concrete mixtures and subsequently curing [11]. Ferrocement is a durable and efficient material. Due to its thin size, ferrocement elements can be used as roofing/flooring elements to cover large spans [10]. Ferrocement is a construction material that proved to have superior qualities of crack control, impact resistance and toughness, largely due to the close spacing and uniform dispersion of reinforcement within the material [5].

The incorporation of silica fume into the normal concrete is a routine one in the present days to produce the tailor-made high strength and high-performance concrete [4]. An attempt is made in

this study to introduce ferrocement which is produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete. The study involves the assessment of compressive and flexural strengths of the novel ferrocement. Siddhesh Navate has studied, the ferrocement panels cast with cement mortar of 1:3 ratio and with w/c ratio of 0.40. Water penetration, sorptivity and resistance to sulphate was determined. The percentage weight loss at 28, 56 and 90 days was found to be 0.28%, 0.32% and 0.33%. The strength loss seen was 6.96%, 6.44% and 6.33% at 28, 56 and 90 days.

Mohamed Ibrahima M has carried out, study on ferrocement secondary roofing. Field thermal performance test shows 25% improved thermal performance, 25% improved thermal comfort and 15% temperature reduction for ferrocement secondary roofing. Improved resistance against accelerated corrosion attack was seen. Due to the addition of inhibitor the durability of ferrocement panels increases. The chloride ion penetration shows 27% reduction in chloride penetration depth. Baskara Sundararaj has shown that, during ACT-AWD there can be an increase in corrosion spots in the 90th cycle in ferrocement panel. Vijayakumar M Javalagaddi has carried out, study on polymer modified silica fume concrete. It is observed that compressive strength, tensile strength and flexural strength of polymer modified silica fume concrete subjected to sulphate attack goes on increasing upto 1.5% polymer in it. Later the strength decreases. Jong Yun Choi has shown that, the water absorption, carbonation and chloride ion penetration resistance were improved as silica fume content and polymer – binder ratio increased. Pothinathan S K M has shown that, at 3% addition of glycoluril formaldehyde, the sorptivity and water absorption capacity improved. Also he has shown that resistance against acid attack is improved at 3% addition of glycoluril formaldehyde. Vikas Srivastava mentions, modulus of elasticity of silica fume concrete is almost similar to that of conventional concrete. Inclusion of silica fume in concrete reduces the permeability of concrete considerably. Alkali silica reaction is reduced in silica fume concrete. Silica fume reduces the chloride penetration in concrete due to pore refinement. Sulphate resistance of silica fume concrete is better than referral concrete.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The cement used was Birla super OPC 53 Grade, the fine aggregate used was river sand, the coarse aggregate used was 20 mm and down size, the polymer used was Dr. Fixit, Styrene Butadiene Rubber Latex. Welded wire mesh and chicken wire mesh was used in single layer and double layer. All these materials were procured from a local distributor from Bangalore. The physical properties of cement were tested in the concrete and highway laboratory, the initial setting time of cement was 25 minutes, final setting time of 400 minutes, consistency of 33%, fineness of 4.33 and specific gravity of 3.15. river sand was used as fine aggregate with fineness modulus of 2.58 and specific gravity of 2.65. The coarse aggregate used was 20 mm and a down size, Angular shaped and specific gravity of 2.74. Silica fume was procured from Tamil Nadu, India.

Sample preparation

The concrete mix was done for M30 in accordance with IS 10262-2019 Code book. The proportion of 1:1.88:3.71 ratios were calculated referring the code book. Initially, 3% SBR Latex polymer was mixed in the concrete. Figures 1 to 12 show the various materials and stages of sample preparation.

Figure 1: OPC 53 grade cement	Figure 2: Fine aggregate	Figure 3: Coarse aggregate
Figure 4: Silica fume	Figure 5: Welded wire mesh	Figure 6: Chicken wire mesh
Figure 7: Water	Figure 8: Dr Fixit polymer	Figure 9: Samples under curing

Figure 10: Samples under Vibration	Figure 11: Weighing of samples	Figure 12: Beam samples

Experimental Work

Compressive strength test: The cubes of size 150x150x150 mm were cast and tested as per IS 516-1959 code book.

$$\text{compressive strength} = \frac{\text{Load}}{\text{Area}} \quad (1)$$

where Load = P in N, Area = 150x150= 2250 mm². The cubes were weighed after 28 days of curing and tested in Compression Testing Machine (CTM) for compression. First set of 21 samples were tested with one layer wire mesh and second set of 21 samples were tested with two layer wire mesh. The samples were tested and tabulation was done. Figures 13 and 14 show the testing of cubes for compression.

Figure 13: Compression testing machine	Figure 14: Cube sample under CTM machine

Flexural strength test: The beams of size 100x100x500 mm were cast and tested as per IS 516-1959.

$$\text{Flexural strength} = \frac{PL}{bd^2} \quad (2)$$

where P = Load in N, L = Length of the beam= 400mm, b= breadth of the beam = 100mm, d = depth of the beam = 100mm. The beams were weighed after 28 days of curing and tested in Universal Testing Machine (UTM) for flexure. First set of 21 samples were tested with one layer

wire mesh and second set of 21 samples were tested with two layer wire mesh. The samples were tested and tabulation was done (refer Figures 15 and 16).

Figure 15: Universal testing machine

Figure 16: Beam sample under UTM

Shear strength test: The L sized specimens of size 150x60x90 mm were cast and tested.

$$\text{Shear strength} = \frac{\text{Failure load}}{\text{Area}} \quad (3)$$

Where, Failure load = $\frac{PL_1}{(L_1+L_2)}$, Where P= Load in N, $L_1=25\text{mm}$, $L_2=25\text{mm}$, A =Area of shear surface= $150 \times 60 \text{ mm}^2$. The specimens were weighed after 28 days of curing and tested in Compression Testing Machine (CTM) with a separate shear test setup attached for shear. First set of 21 samples were tested with one layer wire mesh and second set of 21 samples were tested with two layer wire mesh. The samples were tested and tabulation was done (refer Figures 17 and 18).

Figure 17: Cracking of shear specimen

Figure 18: Cracked specimen

Acidic attack test: The specimens of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete are immersed in sulphuric acid media of pH = 2 for 90 days after 28 days of curing in water. Every day the pH value of the acidic media was checked and it was maintained constant for 90 days. The pH was adjusted to 2 by adding sulphuric acid if necessary. Compressive strength, flexural strength and shear strength are checked for acidic attack.

Sulphate attack test

The specimens kept in the water for curing for 28 days have been replaced in 10% magnesium sulphate solution for 90 days and then removed and tested for compressive strength, flexural

strength and shear strength. Distilled water is used for making the sulphate solution. The weight loss is checked after the sulphate attack.

Chloride attack test

The specimens kept in the water for curing for 28 days have been replaced in calcium chloride solution for 90 days and then removed and tested for compressive strength, flexural strength and shear strength. The solution is prepared with the help of distilled water. The weight loss is checked after the chloride attack.

Compressive strength test results when subjected to acidic attack

Following table 1 gives the overall results of compressive strength with percentage reduction of compressive strength. The variation of compressive strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 19.

Table:1 Overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Compressive strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after acidic attack	Compressive strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after acidic attack
0%	33.47	36.14	7.39	33.62	37.03	9.21
5%	34.07	36.88	7.62	34.96	37.32	6.32
10%	35.10	37.47	6.33	35.70	38.07	6.23
15%	35.85	38.36	6.54	36.73	39.1	6.06
20%	33.03	34.81	5.11	34.07	35.26	3.37
25%	32.73	34.51	5.16	33.18	35.10	5.47
30%	31.7	34.36	7.74	31.84	34.51	7.74

Fig.19 Variation of compressive strength when subjected to acidic attack

Flexural strength test results when subjected to acidic attack

Following table 2 gives the overall results of flexural strength with percentage reduction of flexural strength. The variation of flexural strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 20.

Table : 2 Overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Flexural strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Flexural strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in flexural strength after acidic attack	Flexural strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Flexural strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in flexural strength after acidic attack
0%	3.95	5.57	29.08	4.32	5.97	27.64
5%	3.99	5.71	30.12	4.43	6.05	26.78
10%	4.16	5.80	28.28	4.62	6.11	24.39
15%	4.54	6.09	25.45	4.68	6.49	27.89
20%	3.82	5.24	27.10	4.37	5.70	23.33
25%	3.76	5.00	24.80	4.12	5.43	24.13
30%	3.59	4.41	18.59	4.01	5.16	22.29

Fig. 20 Variation of flexural strength when subjected to acidic attack

Shear strength test results when subjected to acidic attack

Following table 3 gives the overall results of shear strength with percentage reduction of shear strength. The variation of shear strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 21.

Table : 3 Overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Shear strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Shear strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after acidic attack	Shear strength with acidic attack (MPa)	Shear strength without acidic attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after acidic attack
0%	7.56	7.93	4.67	7.75	8.15	4.91
5%	8.32	9.03	7.86	9.54	10.17	6.19
10%	8.61	9.81	12.23	9.55	10.31	7.37
15%	9.38	10.20	8.04	9.65	11.04	12.59
20%	7.65	8.44	9.36	8.49	8.92	4.82
25%	7.29	8.09	9.89	8.00	8.38	4.53
30%	7.13	7.88	9.52	7.32	8.22	10.95

Fig. 21 Variation of shear strength when subjected to acidic attack

Experimental results of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack

Compressive strength test results when subjected to sulphate attack.

Following table 4 give the overall results of compressive strength with percentage increase or decrease of compressive strength. The variation of compressive strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 22.

Table: 4 Overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack.

	Ferrocement with one layer mesh	Ferrocement with two layer mesh
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Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Compressive strength with sulphate attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without sulphate attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after sulphate attack	Compressive strength with sulphate attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without sulphate attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after sulphate attack
0%	34.36	36.14	4.93	35.10	37.03	5.21
5%	34.81	36.88	5.61	35.70	37.32	4.34
10%	35.99	37.47	3.95	36.29	38.07	4.68
15%	36.88	38.36	3.86	37.77	39.10	3.40
20%	33.18	34.81	4.68	34.96	35.26	0.85
25%	33.03	34.51	4.29	33.92	35.10	3.36
30%	32.29	34.36	6.02	33.18	34.51	3.85

Fig.22 Variation of compressive strength when subjected to sulphate attack

Flexural strength test results when subjected to sulphate attack

Following table 5 give the overall results of flexural strength with percentage increase or decrease of flexural strength. The variation of flexural strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 23.

Table :5 Overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Flexural strength	Flexural strength	Percentage reduction in flexural	Flexural strength with	Flexural strength	Percentage reduction in flexural
0%	34.36	36.14	4.93	35.10	37.03	5.21
5%	34.81	36.88	5.61	35.70	37.32	4.34
10%	35.99	37.47	3.95	36.29	38.07	4.68
15%	36.88	38.36	3.86	37.77	39.10	3.40
20%	33.18	34.81	4.68	34.96	35.26	0.85
25%	33.03	34.51	4.29	33.92	35.10	3.36
30%	32.29	34.36	6.02	33.18	34.51	3.85

	with sulphate attack (MPa)	without sulphate attack (MPa)	strength after sulphate attack	sulphate attack (MPa)	without sulphate attack (MPa)	strength after sulphate attack
0%	4.21	5.57	24.42	4.54	5.97	23.95
5%	4.07	5.71	28.72	4.23	6.05	30.08
10%	4.44	5.80	23.45	4.65	6.11	23.90
15%	4.56	6.09	25.12	4.87	6.49	24.96
20%	4.39	5.24	16.22	4.50	5.70	21.05
25%	4.31	5.00	13.80	4.21	5.43	22.47
30%	3.73	4.41	15.42	4.14	5.16	19.77

Fig.23 Variation of flexural strength when subjected to sulphate attack

Shear strength test results when subjected to sulphate attack

Following table 6 give the overall results of shear strength with percentage increase or decrease of shear strength. The variation of shear strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 24.

Table : 6 Overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Shear strength with sulphate attack (MPa)	Shear strength without sulphate attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after sulphate attack	Shear strength with sulphate attack (MPa)	Shear strength without sulphate attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after sulphate attack
0%	7.63	7.93	3.78	7.86	8.15	3.56

5%	8.71	9.03	3.54	9.65	10.17	5.11
10%	8.73	9.81	11.01	9.73	10.31	5.63
15%	9.51	10.20	6.76	9.82	11.04	11.05
20%	7.89	8.44	6.52	8.60	8.92	3.59
25%	7.42	8.09	8.28	8.12	8.38	3.10
30%	7.49	7.88	4.95	7.52	8.22	8.52

Fig. 24 Variation of shear strength when subjected to sulphate attack

Experimental results of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to chloride attack.

Compressive strength test results when subjected to chloride attack.

Following table 7 give the overall results of compressive strength with percentage increase or decrease of compressive strength. The variation of compressive strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 25.

Table : 7 Overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete subjected to chloride attack and without chloride attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Compressive strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after	Compressive strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Compressive strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in compressive strength after
5%	8.71	9.03	3.54	9.65	10.17	5.11
10%	8.73	9.81	11.01	9.73	10.31	5.63
15%	9.51	10.20	6.76	9.82	11.04	11.05
20%	7.89	8.44	6.52	8.60	8.92	3.59
25%	7.42	8.09	8.28	8.12	8.38	3.10
30%	7.49	7.88	4.95	7.52	8.22	8.52

			chloride attack			chloride attack
0%	35.55	36.14	1.63	36.73	37.03	0.81
5%	35.85	36.88	2.79	36.29	37.32	2.76
10%	36.73	37.47	1.97	37.32	38.07	1.97
15%	38.07	38.36	0.76	38.21	39.1	2.28
20%	34.21	34.81	1.72	35.11	35.26	0.43
25%	33.92	34.51	1.71	34.81	35.10	0.83
30%	33.62	34.36	2.15	34.21	34.51	0.87

Fig.25 Variation of compressive strength when subjected to chloride attack

Flexural strength test results when subjected to chloride attack

Following table 8 give the overall results of flexural strength with percentage increase or decrease of flexural strength. The variation of flexural strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 26.

Table : 8 Overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete subjected to chloride attack and without chloride attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Flexural strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Flexural strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in flexural strength after chloride attack	Flexural strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Flexural strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in flexural strength after chloride attack
0%	4.37	5.57	21.54	4.67	5.97	21.78
5%	4.16	5.71	27.15	4.46	6.05	26.28

10%	4.70	5.80	18.97	4.78	6.11	21.77
15%	4.97	6.09	18.39	5.07	6.49	21.88
20%	4.62	5.24	11.83	4.68	5.70	17.89
25%	4.40	5.00	12.00	4.45	5.43	18.05
30%	3.90	4.41	11.56	4.26	5.16	17.44

Fig. 26 Variation of flexural strength when subjected to chloride attack

Shear strength test results when subjected to chloride attack

Following table 9 give the overall results of shear strength with percentage increase or decrease of shear strength. The variation of shear strength is depicted in the form of graph as shown in fig 27.

Table : 9 Overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete subjected to chloride attack and without chloride attack.

Percentage replacement of cement by silica fume	Ferrocement with one layer mesh			Ferrocement with two layer mesh		
	Shear strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Shear strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after chloride attack	Shear strength with chloride attack (MPa)	Shear strength without chloride attack (MPa)	Percentage reduction in shear strength after chloride attack
0%	7.77	7.93	2.02	7.99	8.15	1.96
5%	8.86	9.03	1.88	9.86	10.17	3.05
10%	8.82	9.81	10.09	9.89	10.31	4.07
15%	9.67	10.20	5.20	9.91	11.04	10.24
20%	7.97	8.44	5.57	8.74	8.92	2.02

25%	7.75	8.09	4.20	8.17	8.38	2.51
30%	7.62	7.88	3.30	7.62	8.22	7.30

Fig.27 Variation of shear strength when subjected to chloride attack

OBSERVATIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

Following observations are made based on the study conducted.

- Table 1 gives the overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack of pH 2 for 90 days. Fig 19 shows the variation of compressive strength when subjected to acidic attack. It is observed that the compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to acidic attack. After 15% replacement the compressive strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of compressive strength is 35.85 MPa and the percentage reduction in the compressive strength after acidic attack is 6.54 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of compressive strength and percentage reduction in compressive strength after acidic attack are found to be 36.73 MPa and 6.06% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of mesh.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of acids.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after acidic attack is found to be 6.54% and 6.06% respectively.

2. It is also observed from table 1 and fig 19 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of higher compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

3. Table 2 gives the overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack of pH 2 for 90 days. Fig 20 shows the variation of flexural strength when subjected acidic attack. It is observed that the flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to acidic attack. After 15% replacement the flexural strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of flexural strength is 4.54 MPa and the percentage reduction in the flexural strength after acidic attack is 25.45%. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of flexural strength and percentage reduction in flexural strength after acidic attack are found to be 4.68 MPa and 27.89% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of acids.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The

corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after acidic attack is found to be 25.45% and 27.89% respectively.

4. It is also observed from table 2 and fig 20 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of higher flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

5. Table 3 gives the overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to acidic attack of pH 2 for 90 days. Fig 21 shows the variation of shear strength when subjected acidic attack. It is observed that the shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to acidic attack. After 15% replacement the shear strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of shear strength is 9.38 MPa and the percentage reduction in the shear strength after acidic attack is 8.04%. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of shear strength and percentage reduction in shear strength after acidic attack are found to be 9.65 MPa and 12.59% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of acids.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after acidic attack is found to be 8.04% and 12.59% respectively.

6. It is also observed from table 3 and fig 21 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the

form of higher shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the acidic media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

7. Table 4 gives the overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 22 shows the variation of compressive strength when subjected to sulphate attack. It is observed that the compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to sulphate attack. After 15% replacement the compressive strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of compressive strength is 36.88 MPa and the percentage reduction in the compressive strength after sulphate attack is 3.86 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of compressive strength and percentage reduction in compressive strength after sulphate attack are found to be 37.77 MPa and 3.40% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of sulphates. Due to the addition of silica fume the amount of Ca(OH)_2 reduces which reduces the permeability and also reduces the ingress of sulphates. It also lessens the total heat of hydration and enhances the resistance to chemicals.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after sulphate attack is found to be 3.86% and 3.40% respectively.

8. It is also observed from table 4 and fig 22 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of higher compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer

modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

9. Table 5 gives the overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 23 shows the variation of flexural strength when subjected to sulphate attack. It is observed that the flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to sulphate attack. After 15% replacement the flexural strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of flexural strength is 4.56 MPa and the percentage reduction in the flexural strength after sulphate attack is 25.12 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of flexural strength and percentage reduction in flexural strength after sulphate attack are found to be 4.87 MPa and 24.96% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of sulphates. Due to the addition of silica fume the amount of Ca(OH)_2 reduces which reduces the permeability and also reduces the ingress of sulphates. It also lessens the total heat of hydration and enhances the resistance to chemicals.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after sulphate attack is found to be 25.12% and 24.96% respectively.

10. It is also observed from table 5 and fig 23 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of higher flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified

silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

11. Table 6 gives the overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to sulphate attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 24 shows the variation of shear strength when subjected to sulphate attack. It is observed that the shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to sulphate attack. After 15% replacement the shear strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of shear strength is 9.51 MPa and the percentage reduction in the shear strength after sulphate attack is 6.76 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of shear strength and percentage reduction in shear strength after sulphate attack are found to be 9.82 MPa and 11.05% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of sulphates. Due to the addition of silica fume the amount of Ca(OH)_2 reduces which reduces the permeability and also reduces the ingress of sulphates. It also lessens the total heat of hydration and enhances the resistance to chemicals.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after sulphate attack is found to be 6.76% and 11.05% respectively.

12. It is also observed from table 6 and fig 24 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of higher shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the sulphate media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

13. Table 7 gives the overall results of compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to chloride attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 25 shows the variation of compressive strength when subjected to chloride attack. It is observed that the compressive strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to chloride attack. After 15% replacement the compressive strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of compressive strength is 38.07 MPa and the percentage reduction in the compressive strength after chloride attack is 0.76 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of compressive strength and percentage reduction in compressive strength after chloride attack are found to be 38.21 MPa and 2.28% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of chlorides. It also refines the pores and reduces the chloride penetration in concrete which in turn delays the corrosion.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after chloride attack is found to be 0.76% and 2.28% respectively.

14. It is also observed from table 7 and fig 25 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of higher compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

15. Table 8 gives the overall results of flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to chloride attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 26 shows the variation of flexural strength when subjected to chloride attack. It is observed that the flexural strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to chloride attack. After 15% replacement the flexural strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of flexural strength is 4.97 MPa and the percentage reduction in the flexural strength after chloride attack is 18.39 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of flexural strength and percentage reduction in flexural strength after chloride attack are found to be 5.07 MPa and 21.88% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of chlorides. It also refines the pores and reduces the chloride penetration in concrete which in turn delays the corrosion.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after chloride attack is found to be 18.39% and 21.88% respectively.

16. It is also observed from table 8 and fig 26 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of higher flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of

enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

17. Table 9 gives the overall results of shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete when subjected to chloride attack of 10% concentration for 90 days. Fig 27 shows the variation of shear strength when subjected to chloride attack. It is observed that the shear strength of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete go on increasing upto 15% replacement of cement by silica fume when subjected to chloride attack. After 15% replacement the shear strength shows a decreasing trend. Thus the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh shows higher shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume and the corresponding value of shear strength is 9.67 MPa and the percentage reduction in the shear strength after chloride attack is 5.20 %. Similar observation is made in case of ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes. The corresponding value of shear strength and percentage reduction in shear strength after chloride attack are found to be 9.91 MPa and 10.24% respectively for ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes.

This may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume most of the pores available in the matrix may be filled by the silica fume which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate. Also it may be due to the fact that at 15% replacement level the pozzolanic reaction may take place which will result in the production of C-S-H gel which can resist the action of chlorides. It also refines the pores and reduces the chloride penetration in concrete which in turn delays the corrosion.

Thus it may be concluded that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after chloride attack is found to be 5.20% and 10.24% respectively.

18. It is also observed from table 9 and fig 27 that the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of higher shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh. This is true for all the percentage replacement of cement by silica fume.

This may be due to the fact of increase in the area of steel which will not allow the chloride media to penetrate into the concrete matrix.

Thus it may be concluded that ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

CONCLUSIONS

Following conclusions are drawn based on the experimentation conducted.

1. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after acidic attack is found to be 6.54% and 6.06% respectively.
2. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
3. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after acidic attack is found to be 25.45% and 27.89% respectively.
4. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
5. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after acidic attack is found to be 8.04% and 12.59% respectively.
6. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to acidic attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
7. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after sulphate attack is found to be 3.86% and 3.40% respectively.
8. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
9. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after sulphate attack is found to be 25.12% and 24.96% respectively.
10. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
11. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced shear

strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after sulphate attack is found to be 6.76% and 11.05% respectively.

12. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to sulphate attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
13. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the compressive strength after chloride attack is found to be 0.76% and 2.28% respectively.
14. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced compressive strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
15. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibits higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the flexural strength after chloride attack is found to be 18.39% and 21.88% respectively.
16. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced flexural strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.
17. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh or two layers of meshes exhibit higher resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced shear strength at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. The corresponding reduction in the shear strength after chloride attack is found to be 5.20% and 10.24% respectively.
18. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with two layers of meshes exhibit better resistance to chloride attack in the form of enhanced shear strength as compared to the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with one layer of mesh.

SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS

Following salient conclusions may be drawn out of the research work conducted.

1. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete exhibits higher resistance to acidic attack at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. Therefore the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete is recommended in the construction of sewage treatment plants, water treatment plants or in any industrial structures where the structures are likely to come in contact with the acidic media.
2. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete exhibits higher resistance to sulphate attack at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. Therefore the ferrocement

produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete is recommended in the construction of sea shore structures and other structures where the effect of sulphates on the structure is likely to put the structures in distressed condition.

3. The ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete exhibits higher resistance to chloride attack at 15% replacement of cement by silica fume. Therefore the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete is recommended in the construction of sea shore structures and other structures where the effect of sulphates on the structure is likely to put the structures in distressed condition.
4. Based on the research conducted it is recommended to use the ferrocement produced with polymer modified silica fume concrete with 15% silica fume in various prefabricated structures and in the construction of cast in – situ structures. Also this material can withstand the attacks by acid, sulphates or chlorides in a better way. Therefore it is recommended to use the same in structures coming in contact with various chemicals.

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